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**TRANSCENDING ECOLOGICAL ANALYSIS IN KAIYE AGARY'S YELLOW YELLOW,
TANURE OJAIDE'S THE ACTIVIST AND HELON HABILO'S OIL ON WATER.****DOOSUUR LOIS AMIH**amihlois@yahoo.com**08039672777****AONDOVER ALEXIS TSAMBU**aondoover.tsambu@uniabuja.edu.ng**08034689676****ABSTRACT**

The Niger-Delta crisis has generated a sustained literary engagement in response to the socio-political realities of the region. However, despite the tendency of Niger Delta writers to dwell extensively on environmental issues in their works, this work argues that environmental matters cannot be the sole issues pursued in Niger-Delta Literature. Drawing on the ecocritical and sociological theory, this study analyses the interplay of environmental, social, economic and moral issues embedded in these texts. It demonstrates that human greed, political corruption, social irresponsibility and collective complicity are connected to environmental degradation and cannot be examined in isolation. As a literary genre, the novel offers different representations of the Niger-Delta crisis that transcend environmental issues alone. This study therefore, points out that Niger-Delta Literature does not focus on a singular theme but demands an interdisciplinary approach.

Key Words: Niger-Delta Literature, Beyond Ecocriticism, Ecocriticism, sociology of Literature.

INTRODUCTION

The Niger-Delta spans nine coastal southern states in Nigeria; Bayelsa, Rivers, Akwa-Ibom, Cross River, Edo, Delta, Ondo, Abia and Imo. It contains a significant part of Africa's largest mangrove ecosystem and is a great source of natural wealth for Nigeria. Activities of multinational oil and gas companies have led to widespread pollution of land, air and water. According to the Niger Delta Regional Development Master Plan (NDRDMP 2001), the Niger-Delta faces serious environmental degradation and negative effects on local communities due to the exploration and exploitation of oil and gas.

The persistent failure of the Nigerian government to adequately address the developmental needs of the Niger Delta, despite decades of intensive oil extraction, has deepened frustration among the local population. As environmental devastation worsened and basic infrastructure remained neglected, many youths in the region increasingly turned to militancy as a means of compelling state attention to their suffering. Various groups have emerged to fight injustice and ecological destruction, including the Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP), the Ijaw Youth Council, and later the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), which became one of the most prominent militant organizations in the region.

These struggles gradually escalated into what is now widely referred to as the Niger Delta crisis. Continuous oil exploration has resulted in severe pollution of land and waterways, destruction of farmlands and fishing livelihoods, and widespread health hazards. The resulting economic hardship, combined with political marginalization and perceived exploitation by multinational oil companies and the state, transformed the region into a hotspot of social unrest. Consequently, the Niger Delta has witnessed rising incidents of armed violence, insurgency, kidnapping, hostage-taking, oil pipeline vandalism, crude oil theft, and gang conflicts.

Furthermore, prolonged militarization of the region and violent confrontations between armed groups and state security forces have intensified instability. Government complacency, corruption, and inequitable distribution of oil revenue have reinforced feelings of alienation among residents, pushing many into criminal and militant activities as alternative survival strategies. Insecurity, cultism, piracy, and compromised security institutions have further undermined economic productivity and social cohesion. Thus, environmental exploitation has not only degraded the physical ecosystem of the Niger Delta, but has also destabilized its political structures and social relations, turning the region into a prolonged sociopolitical crisis zone.

Despite the gravity of these issues, literary works from this region focus considerably on ecocriticism. This heightened emphasis on ecological themes brings a lack of understanding to the intricate narratives that define the Niger-Delta as well as the multi-dimensional social, political and environmental crises that continue to shape works and lived experiences of these communities, which encourage a cycle of marginalisation, resistance and ecological devastation. Consequently, there is a need to shift from ecocriticism and engage with other themes like resource control, corruption, militancy, identity crisis and others. Much of the focus of the scholarly attention given to the works of writers from the Niger-Delta has been of ecological nature. In fact, sometimes it appears as if a writer from the Niger Delta cannot project any other thematic preoccupation in his or her work than environmental issues. The problem however is that there is hardly any work of art that projects just a thematic concern. Even when a writer sets out to focus on a particular issue, he or she inadvertently throws up a plethora of others which he or she may not have known are existent in the work at all,

and therein lies the beauty of art. However, the inordinate concentration on espousing ecological themes in Niger Delta creativity makes one to wonder whether or not there is any other message in the literary creativity of this region beyond ecological concern, this paper proposes to find out by identifying features that make Niger-Delta literature distinct, determining how much literature from this region reflects not just sectional but national and or global issues and explore the experiences of the Niger-Delta people as reflected in the selected texts.

Yellow Yellow by Kaine Agary, The Activist by Tanure Ojaide and Oil on Water by Helon Habila have been selected for this paper, thereby identifying these authors who are arguably among the most popular voices of the Niger Delta region, to give the study its credibility. The selected texts are relevant to this study as they address a wide range of issues including ecological degradation, pointing out how many of the issues have evolved over the years and newer issues that have come up in recent times in the Niger-Delta.

This study therefore, undertakes to find out whether or not there exists thematic concerns of interest in the literary creativity of Niger-Delta writers outside of ecological degradation. It is for these reasons that this paper is significant.

Oseghale Francis focuses on the ecocritical view in 'The Ecocritical Analysis of Kaine Agary's Yellow Yellow'. He points out the harm the oil companies have brought upon the Niger-Delta and its people when oil spillage destroys farms animals and aquatic life and Bibi is no longer able to cater for her daughter Zilayefa.. He points out that through effective characterization the author brings out the ecological degradation and pollution in the region. Samuel Adewumi explores ecocritical issues in Agary's YellowYellow to determine the level of degradation in that region. He brings up concerns regarding pollution, contamination, food poisoning and the damage the environment brings to health. He notes the evil consequences of the discovery of oil in the Niger-Delta which has become a curse because of these exploitations. These reviews still focus on ecological damage as the driving force and the dominant issue in the selected novels. They use ecocriticism as a framework while the present study goes beyond ecocriticism by further encompassing the issues mentioned above.

Alpaslan Toker and Safiya Jega write on 'Crimes against Nature in Ojaide's The Activist' and reveal the pertinent environmental challenges bedevilling the African society in the postcolonial era. They point out man as the wide link to environmental damage and ecosystem collapse. The work centres on examining how the author portrays environmental degradation, human impact on nature, and societal responses to ecological crises within their respective narratives. The analysis explores themes such as environmental justice, sustainability, and the ethical implications of human-nature relationships as depicted in the text. The study analyzes the use of ecocritical components and elements contained in the text, focusing on African Literature in general, while this research specifically focuses on the Niger Delta region in Nigeria. According to Toker, Ojaide portrays the disillusionment of the marginalized and dehumanized people of the Niger-Delta due to environmental decay caused by oil spillage and carbon emissions caused by the mining of oil. The protagonist's major concern is to restore the environment in his community. The approach in the present topic under study involves examining how these texts critique or challenge existing power structures, economic inequalities related to natural resources, and cultural responses to environmental change specific to the Niger Delta. Toker and Jega's analysis focus specifically on the environmental themes within the novels of Ojaide and Armah, whereas this paper covers a wider range of literary works and explores more diverse socio-political issues. Toker and Jega's work as well as this present study share a common focus on environmental issues and their representation in literature, albeit within different geographical and socio-political contexts. The ecocritical analysis by Toker and Jega employs

traditional ecocritical methods, such as close reading of texts to uncover environmental themes. This study, in contrast, incorporates ecocriticism as well as socio-political and cultural perspectives to analyze the literature within its broader context. They both involve critical engagement with literature to uncover deeper meanings related to human interactions with the natural world and the consequences of environmental degradation. This study reinforces and expands the analysis of Niger Delta texts, including socio-political issues, as Toker and Jega's study is limited in comparative scope.

In 'A Marxist Reading of Tanure Ojaide's' *The Activist*', Joseph Osita looks at the text from a Marxist view. In line with the marxist ideals, Osita reveals the untold hardship of the Niger-Delta people and their environment from the immoral exploitation of oil by oil companies. As an ideology that originated from the writings of Karl Marx and Federick Engels, it advocates for a revolution in favour of the proletariat in a capitalist society. Advocates of Marxist ideology believe that a typical capitalist society is partitioned between the haves and the have-nots, the rich and the poor, the employers and the employees in which those with the advantage of wealth and power exploit and oppress the havenots. Osita depicts atrocious activities of Bell and O&G Companies against the people of the Niger Delta. It is a strong portrayal of oppression, exploitation, and degradation of the poor by the bourgeoisie, Bell, and O & G in collaboration with the Federal Military Government. The Novel, like every other Marxist text, is grouped into the oppressor and the oppressed. Both works address their respective subjects (Joseph's Osita's work on *The Activist* and the present study) from distinct theoretical frameworks and perspectives. One from a marxist view focusing on issues like class struggle, economic determinism, and social inequality, while the other examines environmental themes, ecological concerns, and the relationship between literature and the environment, and also the Niger-Delta and Nigerian society at large. The focus on both studies also differs as the emphasis in the study on the Marxist reading is on socio-economic structures, exploitation, activism, and resistance, while this study gears away from environmental degradation and focuses on sustainability, eco-justice, and possibly cultural or indigenous responses to ecological issues in the Niger Delta literature. Environmental degradation in the Niger-Delta is not merely ecological, it is embedded in resource control, political domination, and capitalism. In analytical Methods, the Marxist employs dialectical analysis, historical materialism, and critiques of capitalism and colonialism within the context of the novel, while the current study utilises oil exploitation as a political economic system not just as harm to the environment to expose injustice where the communities in this region bear the costs of national and global energy demands which is linked to human rights, ethics and justice not just ecology. It also points out how the authors studied in this research resist, negotiate and also re-imagine what the future of these communities will be. While many works focus on representations of nature, this study foregrounds power relations, shows how the locals understand, produce and validate knowledge based on their culture, history, environment and lived experiences and shows how literature serves as a counter-discourse to state and corporate narratives thereby linking literature with environmental science or policy.

In the '*The Storyworld Accord*', Erin James explores how Helon Habila and Ben Okri narratives reflect the ecological and cultural landscapes of the Niger-Delta. In *Oil on Water*, Habila uses a disjointed narrative and different perspectives to reveal the complexity of the environmental crisis. James argues that this narrative technique enhances readers' understanding of the nature of environmental issues in the region. This is related to the present study through its shared focus on how narratives shape human understanding and engagement with environmental issues. Both studies recognize how literature can influence our perception of the environment and our attitude towards it. Attention is drawn to the human and ecological impact of oil extraction,

which draws on ecocriticism. However, the present study differs, in that it goes further to examine issues beyond these.

Iliya Lomka kopdiya in 'Exploring Ecocriticism in Chimeka Garrick's *Tomorrow Died Yesterday* and Helon Habila's *Oil on Water*' points out the novel's advocacy of the need for humanity to protect the environment. It reveals and suggests that harming the natural environment destroys the future in the present, as the environment is an integral part of our future, and destroying it brings an end to humanity's destiny. Kopdiya also focuses on literature set in the Niger-Delta, depicting environmental and sociopolitical issues resulting from oil exploitation in the region. He employs ecocritical approaches to examine these selected texts, highlighting the environmental destruction and human suffering caused by the oil industry. He analyzes how storytelling raises awareness of environmental harm in the Niger Delta and the need to address environmental injustice. Both novels portray environmental degradation caused by oil exploration. The message revolves around highlighting the devastating impact of this industry on the environment, communities, and individuals. It highlights the themes of exploitation, corruption, and the human cost associated with unchecked resource extraction, urging readers to consider the ethical and ecological implications of these activities. This paper studies a broader range of texts and analysis to identify overarching trends and sociopolitical implications within the region's texts. Kopdiya focuses on ecocritical analysis, while this study integrates interdisciplinary perspectives, seeking to place the Niger-Delta texts within larger socio-environmental and cultural frameworks. This study draws on various academic disciplines, including politics, ecology, sociology, and history. It also highlights the contribution of the Niger-Delta literature to ecocriticism. Cajetan Iheka's 'Naturalizing Africa' investigates the representation of ecological degradation in African Literature with a focus on the Niger-Delta novels. Iheka examines how authors depict the historical context of colonialism and its enduring impact on the environment. He highlights that Helon Habila incorporates elements of historical fiction to trace the roots of contemporary environmental issues back to colonial days. He contends that this is crucial to understanding the ongoing struggles for environmental justice in the Niger-Delta. Iheka's work offers a broader comparative analysis of ecological violence and postcolonial resistance across Africa, providing a different scope and focus, whereas the present work delves into socio-political issues in the Niger Delta region, using ecocriticism as a launchpad into other underlying issues. Both contribute to ecocriticism, but the emphasis and goals are distinct. Iheka's study focuses on violent human resistance and argues that in postcolonial Africa, the ecocritical standpoint should account for responsibility towards nature. He aims to redirect African ecocriticism to care for not just humans but also animals, land, and water. The present study transcends ecocriticism, which focuses on environmental issues and explores social, cultural, and economic concerns; it examines the interface between human nature and the socio-political context.

Through the eyes of different scholars and critics, we find the complex nature of environmental issues that the Niger-Delta has been known for. It is also clear that many critics have done some work on ecocriticism and have identified some issues that are socio-political but these are drowned by ecological damage which has been a known plague in the Niger-Delta. It is by filling this important gap that this work will help in understanding how interconnected the issues in the Niger-Delta are and how some of the issues are not ecological as many critics would want us to believe.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Ecocriticism and the sociological school of literary criticism have been employed in this study as the framework for analysis. The theories are the anchor for this enquiry because they offer a comprehensive approach. Ecocriticism delves into the ecological dimensions to address environmental concerns, and with it ecological content can be identified in this study, it is only by identifying these,

that other issues can be pointed out. The sociological theory of literature allows for a deeper exploration of the social structures, power dynamics, and cultural contexts depicted in the literature. This dual framework allows for a distinct analysis to examine how environmental and social factors intersect and influence each other within the narrative, to give a deeper understanding of the complexities that are inherent in the region. This approach considers how societal factors shape and are shaped by the narratives, offering insights into broader issues such as culture, economy, colonialism, globalization, and social justice.

William Ruecket coined the term ecocriticism in 1978 in his essay titled "Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocritics". The term gained popularity in the mid-nineties when it became a genre worked out by Western Language Association (WLA). These associations emerged as a response to increasing environmental concerns, focusing on the relationship between literature and the physical environment. The relevance of ecocriticism to modern day literature cannot be overemphasized in the face of the present global environmental challenges and concerns. According to Habeeb and Habeeb, ecocriticism investigates the relation between humans and the natural world in literature, the way in which environmental issues, cultural issues concerning the environment and attitudes towards nature are presented and analyzed, and how individuals in society behave and react in relation to nature and ecological aspects (504). They identify objectives of ecocriticism some of which are to understand man, through literature, as an inseparable part of the environment and his ability to alter this relationship while also being susceptible to its influence, to gain a broader understanding of literature and environment and their role in society and to show concern for the present day issues of threat to wild life, global warming, industrial pollution, depletion of natural resources, population explosion etc. these point us to the happenings in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

Glotfelty and Fromm's *The Ecocriticism Reader* defined ecocriticism as the study of literature and the environment from an interdisciplinary point of view, while Graham Huggan and Helen Tiffin's emphasize the need for ecocriticism to incorporate postcolonial perspectives, focusing on the environmental impact of colonialism and neo-colonialism (12).

Arne Naess, a Norwegian philosopher introduced deep ecology a radical version of environmentalism in 1973, then United States environmentalists, Bill Devall and George Sessions developed it in the 1980's. Naess wants humans 'to go beyond the factual level of ecology as a science to a deeper level of self-awareness and 'Earth wisdom' (95). She points out that this is a call for man to show concern for both living and nonliving things, emphasizing the role of the individual who is invited to behave as a citizen of the World and Earth and to take responsibility for it (96-97).

The sociological theory of literature emphasizes the extrinsic view that art is a function of the society and that it can be used as a tool to interpret and transform society. Literature reflects the economy, relationship, attitude, morals, social class, political issues, religion, emotion, expectations, suffering, hopes and aspirations of a people, it shapes the political, religious, and economic forces in the society giving it impetus, this is why it is a vital tool used by writers to criticize the social and political situations and ills of its society. In the words of Roshni Duhan, 'Literature is a corrective agent as it mirrors the society with a view to making society realize its mistakes and making amends'. It projects the virtues and good values in society that people can emulate. Prominent propounders include Georg Lukács, he emphasized literature's role in reflecting social contradictions, Lukács, a Hungarian Marxist philosopher, developed his sociological theory of literature in the early to mid-20th century. He argued that literature reflects the social contradictions and conflicts of its time. In his work *History and Class Consciousness* and *The Theory of the Novel*, he emphasized the importance of the novel as a form that captures the essence of societal dynamics and believed that literature could serve as

a tool for understanding and critiquing society's structures and values. He explores the idea of the usefulness of literature when he says:

The social determinants of an artistic creation depend upon the degree to which the writers are bound up with the life of the community, to the extent they take part in the struggle going on around them, or they are merely passive observers of the events (10).

Pierre Bourdieu on the other hand focused on the cultural capital embedded in literary works and their reception. As a French sociologist, he introduced the concept of cultural resources, which emphasises the role of cultural resources, such as knowledge, skills, and education, in shaping social inequalities. In his book *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgment of Taste*, Bourdieu analyzed how literary taste and consumption patterns are influenced by social class and cultural background. He argued that literature serves as a means of cultural reproduction, reinforcing existing social hierarchies. His influential work on the sociology of literature began in the 1960s and continued throughout his career. In his work on literature, Bourdieu argues that literary taste and preferences are influenced by one's social position and cultural background. He suggests that literary consumption serves as a form of social distinction, where individuals utilize their cultural capital to signal their social status. Bourdieu's sociological theory of literature emphasizes the intersection of literature, culture, and social hierarchy, illuminating how literary tastes and practices reflect broader social structures. Some critics, such as Terry Eagleton, oppose Bourdieu's views for oversimplifying complex cultural phenomena or neglecting the role of individual agency in artistic creation. Edward Said also challenges Bourdieu's views as it focus on the internal dynamics of Western Literature, arguing instead for a broader consideration. Each has contributed unique perspectives on how literature intersects with society, culture, and politics, these theorists offer valuable insights into how literature interacts with and influences the social fabric.

TEXTUAL ANALYSIS

Yellow Yellow

The novel *Yellow, Yellow* tells of Zilafeya, a mixed race girl raised in a small village by a single mother at the time of oil boom in the seventies. Even though it explores issues of ecology it also tells of the effects of the contact between coastal communities and the sea in the Niger Delta. Like in *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*, Asiam town serves as coastal outpost like the community in *Yellow Yellow* showing that even before the advent of oil, this region has constantly suffered violence which has resulted in the sexualisation of the female body. It exposes the deprivations the women experience and the result of these contacts with foreign nationals. Zilayefa is taunted as 'Ashawo pikin', *Yellow, Yellow*, 'born troway' because of her mixed heritage and is believed to be a product of a sexually polluted mother who tries to escape poverty by having sexual relations with a sailor. She plans to escape from the village deciding that an out-of- townner would be her ticket out of her desperate existence, she finds Sergio a Caucasian, who she thinks will save her from her 'claustrophobic village" (17). However, Sergio ends up leaving without a word. Thereafter, Pastor Ikechukwu links her up with Madam George in Port Harcourt; a city with bustling activities where she hopes to find a better life.

Transcending Ecocritical interpretations in Kaine Agary's Yellow Yellow.

The first major thematic concern that is not ecocritical in nature is that of poverty, sexuality and search for a father. The protagonist experiences a lot of hardship like her mother before her who

returns to her village after getting pregnant by a Greek sailor. Their farmland is contaminated by oil spill and like other young girls in her group Zilayefa moves to Port Harcourt for better opportunities. She is vulnerable as she desires to have a father figure, considering that she does not know who her father is. She is lucky to find guardians in Port Harcourt but still falls for an old wealthy and retired admiral in the Nigerian Navy. Retired Admiral Alaowei Amalayefa sponsors her lifestyle leading her into a world of sex and lots of abortions. While Admiral sleeps, she lays awake admiring how handsome he is: 'with his dimples and the sprinkles of grey hair in it' (138). She longs for him "not because of the money Emem hinted at, but because I was hoping that the relationship would give me a taste of close paternal affection that I never had" (138). She also remarks that "I wanted Admiral for more than money; I was yearning for an emotional bond with him" (149).

She confesses that she thought giving up her virginity to Admiral will endear him to her but he is only interested in her as a plaything. This is the same for many of the young girls looking to find wealthy men, especially white men, to make their lives better. Zilayefa confirms this: "when I got to Port Harcourt, most of the young girls who were looking to escape their poverty were looking to white men to rescue them" (167).

While in the village, the young girls have nothing else to do to make out a living like the young men, Zilayefa's peers, Ebiere gets pregnant and they visit another classmate who just puts to birth. They speak of the father of the new born who had no means of livelihood and was killed when caught up in the wrong feud and Ebiere does not also have any means of making money. Bibi tells her daughter of days in her youth where every husband was expected to give his wife a canoe that he had crafted himself and the wife would use this to earn a living. The men have lost their means of making a living like the women and they become oppressive as the tension and conflicts bring more frustration to the people.

The men are more attracted to the mullatos because of their light skin. As Zilayefa says: "our crop of yellows was full of variety, coloured by Filipinos, the Chinese, the British and the Americans who worked in the oil sector" (74). They are patronised by rich men who do not consider marrying them because they are born out of casual relationships with foreigners and may be easy to sleep with like their mothers. We see her follow in similar steps like her mother. Moving to Port Harcourt from the village hoping to get a better life only to find that "the same poverty and discontent in my village that I was running away from was present in Port Harcourt" (99) like her mother before her she falls for Admiral and the white Sergio, unlike her mother she aborts the baby she conceives as a result of her involvement with both men.

The Activist

The Activist by Tanure Ojaide is a novel that delves into the social, political, and environmental struggles of the Niger Delta region. The Activist refers to a dedicated and principled activist who returns to Nigeria from the United States after study. With a strong sense of justice and responsibility, he is deeply disturbed by the exploitation of his homeland by multinational oil companies and the corruption of the Nigerian government. In a place where oil wealth is abundant, there is environmental degradation, poverty, and political neglect.

Upon returning, Rufus takes up with the university in his home state but quickly becomes disillusioned by the greed, pollution, and lack of accountability of the oil corporations in the Niger Delta. He leaves the corporate world and joins forces with other social crusaders to fight against injustice. The Activist and his group use peaceful protest, legal channels, and community mobilization to challenge both the oil companies and the government.

As the story unfolds, he faces threats, betrayals, and personal challenges, including strained relationships and the dangers that come with opposing powerful interests. Yet, he remains steadfast in his cause. The novel captures not only the political tension but also the personal cost of activism in a corrupt society.

Transcending Ecocritical interpretations in Tanure Ojaide's The Activist.

One of the issues that is not ecological in nature is the total disregard for national laws in *The Activist*. Bell oil, the leading oil corporation in *The Activist* focuses on oil exploration and maximum profit, so much so that they bestow powers upon themselves to do as they choose. Their acquired economic power gives them the audacity to neglect every corporate social responsibility which should cater for the needs of the people whose resources they are empowered by. Instead, the Niger Delta people are impoverished and brought into conditions that weaken the thought of resistance. Ojaide tells that:

The pipes had been shoddily laid to the oil installations a long time ago when oil was discovered in the area ... the pipes were leaking. These pipes crossed playgrounds of children, crossed cassava farms of the women, and even went through many parts of the village. Residential homes stood on both sides of pipelines...when there was this outburst of crude oil that easily caught fire, the village was burnt to the ground. (154-155).

The company knows the dangers of oil blowouts, yet it fences the entire village with oil pipes. They fail to provide fire fighting equipment to the villages to prepare for days when blowouts may occur. Bell oil takes advantage of the poverty stricken underdeveloped minority setting, knowing well that these same actions cannot be taken in Western countries.

Bell Oil is a fictional representation of oil companies operating in Nigeria and shows how these companies function without impunity, they are protected by Nigerian military operatives, their activities constantly endanger the lives of the people, a trend that shows up in the novels selected for this study. The Laws in the novel are complicit as the companies violate them either negligently or collaboratively. these laws are meant to protect the people and the environment but are ignored just for their gain. The traditional rulers and politicians are overtaken by corruption and forget about their roles as cultural custodians, further enabling the erosion of traditional authority.

Another issue is the disregard for cultural norms in that area. The Women Delta Forum goes on a peaceful protest against environmental damage and is deliberately thrown tear gas. The narrator says:

The world was denied the spectacle of a naked parade of old women before the oil terminal and the nearby flow station. Mask-wearing navy personnel with the assistance of retired marines kept by Bell Oil Company in their own coordinated plan overwhelmed the island with tear gas and a type of gas nobody knew its name but made people dizzy and mindless (215).

They go out to protest against the after effects of the gaseous pollution which causes pregnant women to go into sudden labour, babies to cough relentlessly, leaving the old wheezing, eyes itching and they get a high dose of another poisonous gas. Even with these injustices the government allows Bell oil to still continue operations. The act of women protesting carries deep cultural weight, symbolizing collective moral condemnation and using tear gas to prevent the event not only violates the women's human rights but desecrates the regions' custom and system of resistance.

The people of the Niger Delta are exposed to pollution but those who cause the pollution are protected from it. This consolidates Merchant's position that 'hierarchical differences within human society affect the character of environmental problems, as not all classes and ethnic groups are equal before environmental pollution' (76)

The social relations that expose the Niger Delta and its people to environmental hazards are encouraged by racist and class tendencies, with the support of the Government. Reed says that 'class stratification, domestic and international racial prejudice are enablers of larger environmental irresponsibility' (149). The Government and its agents encourage the subjugation of the Niger Delta. For example, the foreign nationals live far away from the people, in an atmosphere that is much better than where the Niger Delta people live. They do not drink from the greenish ponds the people drink from nor do they suffer from oil leaks and explosions the people suffer from.

Oil on Water

Helon Habila's *Oil on Water* is set in the riverine Niger-Delta region of Nigeria, an area heavily affected by crude oil exploration for both national and global interests. The novel draws on the motif of a journey by water echoing Joseph Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* to explore the darkness within the human soul and its devastating impact on the environment and marginalized communities. The story follows a young journalist who, alongside a veteran reporter named Zaq, sets out to locate militants who have abducted a white woman, Isabella Floode. Their mission is to confirm her survival before ransom negotiations precede.

Transcending Ecocritical interpretations in Helon Habila's *Oil on Water*.

Some of the issues the indigenous people of the Niger Delta have to deal with beyond ecological issues is violence, militancy and resistance. As pollution of the water and land has rendered agriculture nearly impossible and life itself precarious, more alarming is the erosion of respect for human life. The villagers are caught in the crossfire between militants and the military. These communities are the literal and symbolic battleground for conflict. The militants target oil companies to sabotage and then kidnap oil workers like Isabella Floode. They also use armed rebellion to draw attention to their cause. The military on the other hand responds with aggressive crackdowns, raids and bombings, invading the villages while the militants then hide, using the villagers as shields or recruiting the young ones to join their cause. We are told that 'the communities had borne the brunt of oil wars, caught between militants and the military' (34). These communities are exploited by the politics surrounding oil, therefore, they suffer economic collapse, displacement, cultural loss, trauma and even death.

This bleak reality prompts characters like Tamuno to entrust his son, Michael to the journalists, hoping he might find a future elsewhere: 'He no get good future here...I fear say soon him go join the militants' (36). Chief Ibiram's account of their community's transformation further illustrates the deep alienation brought about by environmental devastation. In the past, the villagers lived in abundance and unity, committed to preserving their traditions. However, deceitful tactics by oil companies, supported by government collaborators, eventually displaces them from their ancestral lands.

Another point to note is the lack of basic amenities in the region which is recurrent in Niger-Delta texts. It underscores the harsh realities faced by the local communities despite the fact that great wealth is generated from their land. Habila uses this theme to highlight the fact that government has neglected the region and betrayed the people's hopes. There is a harsh contrast

between the extractions done in the region and the abject poverty the people endure. While oil companies, some local chiefs and corrupt government officials make huge profits, the youth go around unemployed; the communities go without clean water, electricity healthcare or decent infrastructure. They are instead surrounded by pipelines and refineries, polluted rivers, dead fish and toxic air, the houses are destroyed by military raids, villages lay in ruins, clinics and schools are abandoned.

When Zaq and Rufus go in search of the kidnapped Isabel Floode, Zaq is injured and in need of medical attention, but they find none in the village. Rufus tells us 'there was nowhere to take him... the nearest hospital was two days away' (43). This reveals the lack of emergency care in the region. When they finally get to a village with a few inhabitants, we are told:

It was an entire village on stilts, situated by the river on a vast mud flat, which at that moment was under water, so the village appeared to float; narrow passages of water divided one row of huts from the next, like streets. The houses were made from weeping willow bamboos and raffia palms and bits of zinc and plywood and cloth and it seemed anything else the builders were able to lay their hands on. The whole scarecrow settlement looked as if the next strong wind or wave would blow it away (14).

Even the militant camps shows the squalor the people live in. The militants who were once local youths take up arms for this same reason, they are driven by the absence of opportunities and lack of basic services. They live in shack made from rusted zinc and wood scraps, no electricity, no toilets

The lack of these amenities fuels insurgency and the young people join militant groups, it is this fear that Tamuno expresses when he forces his son on the duo. Mr. Floode is able to seduce and take Koko, Salomon's fiancé away because Salomon is poor. As a University graduate, he is forced to take up a menial job as a driver with meagre salary. His poverty comes from being unemployed, a general problem among Niger-Delta youth. They burst pipelines, and siphon fuel; these illegal petrol businesses result in fire outbursts as the drums of fuel are kept in houses at the risk of people's lives.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Agary's *Yellow Yellow*, Ojaide's *Activist* and Habila's *Oil on Water* engage other concerns that interrogate socio-political and cultural issues in the Niger-Delta. Although environmental degradation is a significant motif in these narratives, this study shows that the texts also foreground other pressing realities that shape life in the region. However, many existing critical readings tend to give privilege to ecological readings, often overlooking these additional thematic areas. This study reveals that the selected writers deliberately situate environmental issues within socio-political challenges, ethnic tensions, political instability, leadership failure, economic exploitation and social injustice. These issues are not separate from ecological degradation, they are rather deeply connected. Ecological damage is shown to be an aftermath and catalyst of government failure and entrenched power imbalance.

These novels portray how the neglect of the region, marginalisation and unethical practices of both state and actors and multinational companies further exacerbate ecological damage. Through varied techniques, the authors reveal the lived experiences of individuals whose struggles reflect deeper problems within the region. These narratives collectively underscore that the Niger-Delta cannot be understood through the ecological lens alone, instead, it requires a

holistic interpretation, recognising environmental concerns as inseparable from its socio-political and economic realities.

CONCLUSION

The portrayal of the Niger Delta in *Yellow Yellow*, *The Activist*, and *Oil on Water* shows how complicated and multifaceted the relationship between geography, resource wealth, and socio-political vulnerability is. The region's strategic location and openness to global trade, particularly through oil exploration, have positioned it at the centre of national and international economic interests. However, rather than translating into development and social stability, this exposure has intensified the region's susceptibility to exploitation, neglect, and systemic crises.

Together, these novels prove that the Niger Delta's challenges go far beyond the physical act of oil extraction. While environmental degradation remains a visible and recurring concern, it is portrayed as a symptom of deeper structural failures, including ineffective governance, political corruption, corporate irresponsibility, and the marginalization of local communities. The half-hearted responses to environmental destruction by both state authorities and multinational corporations further entrench these problems, allowing ecological damage to persist alongside social unrest and economic inequality. Ultimately, this study argues that an exclusive ecological reading of Niger Delta literature is insufficient for understanding the full scope of the region's crisis.

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